

CHARTER MANAGEMENT PROCESSES – MANAGEMENT HANDBOOK

CHARTER Deliverable D7.1

Grant Agreement Number: 869471

Project Acronym: CHARTER

Project title: Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in
Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity

Starting Date: 01/08/2020

Project Duration: 48 months

Project Officer: Alberto Zocchi

Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

Leading Author: Coordination team / LAY

Contributing partners: -

Co-financed by the Connecting Europe
Facility of the European Union

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Version 2 (revised after the first review)

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Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

Authors: Sirpa Rasmus (LAY), Bruce Forbes (LAY)

Due Submission Date: 30/09/2020

Actual Submission Date: 30/09/2020

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Status	
Draft	
Final	x

Type		
R	Document, report	x
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	
OTHER		

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. the Commission services)	

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Revision history

Date(s)	Lead author(s)	Comments
1.8.- 30.9.2020	Sirpa Rasmus, Bruce Forbes, and others in the CHARTER Coordination team (LAY)	Numerous drafts circulated within the Coordination team
30.9.2020	Sirpa Rasmus (LAY)	Final version (v1), submitted
30.6.2022	Sirpa Rasmus (LAY)	Final version (v2), revised according the comments given during the first review, submitted

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1 Introduction

The objective of this report is to present the management structure of CHARTER. Content is similar to the CHARTER Management Handbook, which is available to consortium partners through our Eduuni site and on the internal CHARTER webpage:

<https://www.charter-arctic.org/about/contacts/internal/>

2 CHARTER Management Handbook

CHARTER MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE AND DECISION-MAKING

The management structure of CHARTER is described in the figure below. In this document we explain the roles of different management and decision-making bodies of CHARTER and list the contact info needed. In our Consortium Agreement you can find all details and e.g. the rights and responsibilities of partners.

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EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Coordinator is the intermediary between the partners and European Commission / funder. So when partners need to inform EC or have requests/questions, let the coordinator know.

CHARTER contact points at the EC are:

The Project Adviser: Alberto Zocchi, alberto.zocchi@ec.europa.eu

The Legal/financial Adviser: Paul Sescu, paul.sescu@ec.europa.eu

CHARTER PARTNERS AND CONTACT POINTS

Contact point is the person in the partner organization to whom the messages of the coordinator are sent if they are not meant to a specific person/role. Contact person delivers the messages inside her/his organization to all the relevant persons. **Our partners and contact points are as follows:**

No	Short name	Name	Country	Contact points
1	LAY	University of Lapland	Finland	Bruce Forbes bruce.forbes@ulapland.fi
2	NTNU	Norw. Univ. of Science and Technology	Norway	James Speed james.speed@ntnu.no
3	UCL	University College London	UK	Julienne Stroeve j.stroeve@ucl.ac.uk
4	NMBU	Norwegian University of Life Sciences	Norway	Andrei Marin andrei.marin@nmbu.no
5	UOXF	University of Oxford	UK	Marc Macias-Fauria marc.maciasfauria@ouce.ox.ac.uk
6	UH	University of Helsinki	Finland	Jussi Eronen jussi.t.eronen@helsinki.fi
7	UEF	University of Eastern Finland	Finland	Timo Kumpula timo.kumpula@uef.fi
8	BGEOS	b.geos GmbH	Austria	Annett Bartsch annett.bartsch@bgeos.com
9	LBHI	Agricultural University of Iceland	Iceland	Isabel Barrio isabel@lbhi.is
10	FMI	Finnish Meteorological Institute	Finland	Jouni Pulliainen jouni.pulliainen@fmi.fi

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11	UZH	University of Zurich	Switzerland	Gabriela Schaepman-Strub gabriela.schaepman@ieu.uzh.ch
12	UTU	University of Turku	Finland	Nora Fagerholm ncfage@utu.fi
13	WSL	Swiss Fed. Inst. for Forest, Snow and Landscape Res.	Switzerland	Christian Rixen rixen@slf.ch
14	UHAM	University of Hamburg	Germany	Otto Habeck otto.habeck@uni-hamburg.de
15	AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute	Germany	Heidrun Matthes heidrun.matthes@awi.de
16	UiT	The Arctic University of Norway	Norway	Dorothee Ehrich dorothee.ehrich@uit.no
17	UEDIN	University of Edinburgh	UK	Isla Myers-Smith isla.myers-smith@ed.ac.uk
18	NINA	The Norwegian Inst. for Nature Research	Norway	Hans Tømmervik hans.tommervik@nina.fi
19	ULIV	University of Liverpool	UK	Richard Bradshaw Richard.Bradshaw@liverpool.ac.uk
20	AU	Aarhus University	Denmark	Signe Normand signe.normand@bios.au.dk
21	UmU	Umeå University	Sweden	Johan Olofsson johan.olofsson@emg.umu.se

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PROJECT COORDINATOR AND THE PROJECT OFFICE

The Project Coordinator is the executive officer of the project. CHARTER is coordinated by the University of Lapland.

Tasks of the Project Coordinator are:

- take full responsibility for fulfilling the obligations described in the Grant Agreement, including overall and financial management;
- ensure prompt and continuous contact with the EC Project Officer and act as an intermediary with the partners (sign contract and distribute funding);
- ensure a proper integration of all the partners through continuous communication and exchange of knowledge between them;
- keeping the address list of members and other contact persons updated and available;
- coordinate the progress meetings;
- chair the Steering Committee;
- making interface with the EAG members and securing non-disclosure commitments from the members;
- ensuring that gender equality issues are addressed;
- transmitting documents and information connected with the project to any other partner concerned;
- providing, upon request, the parties with official copies or originals of documents;
- coordinate the preparation of scientific and management Periodic Reports;
- arranging any necessary amendments;
- organizing the audit certification.

The Project Office (PO; we call this also as a coordination team) is responsible for the overall project administration, management, communication, and coordination of the entire project. This includes establishing the management structure and procedures, the implementation of actions according to Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, legal issues, data management, financial management, implementation of Quality Assurance and reporting.

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The CHARTER Project Office includes the following functions:

- Reporting to the SC and preparation of project status reports for the EC;
- Ensuring project procedures are in place and followed;
- Coordination of the work packages;
- Arranging project and virtual meetings;
- Monitoring the planning and progress of the defined tasks, deliverables and milestones, and if needed initiating corrective actions;
- Identification and management of risks:
- Financials: Ensuring partners are aware of and follow EC expenditure regulations. Tracking financials and handling any needs for budget reallocations;
- Ensuring timely delivery of all data required by the EC, e.g. for reviews and audits;
- Handling payments made by the EC and their distribution to partner organisations.

The division of responsibilities within the CHARTER Project Office is as follows:

- Bruce Forbes (leader, principal investigator, EC contact point)
- Sirpa Rasmus (project management)
- Kirsi Hannula (financial issues)
- Karol Kowalski (legal issues)
- Markku Heikkilä (communications)
- Petra Falin (ethics)
- Hannu Mikkola (data management/legal aspects)
- Riitta Aikio and Tuija Katermaa (LAY internal management)

Leena Leppänen and Teresa Komu will support the project management from 1.1.2021 onwards.

All emails have the form firstname.familyname@ulapland.fi.

The Project Office (coordination team) meets monthly, according to the needs of the consortium and its management and decision-making bodies.

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MAIL LISTS AND E-DUUNI WORKSPACE

We have some mail lists / list servers made and updated as needed:

CHARTER_legal_signatories@ulapland.fi (partner legal signatories)

CHARTER_financial_signatories@ulapland.fi (partner financial signatories)

CHARTER_EC_Portal@ulapland.fi (everyone listed in the EC portal)

CHARTER_contact_points@ulapland.fi (partner contact points)

CHARTER_researchers@ulapland.fi (all researchers involved; updated as new post docs start)

The contact information for certain roles (e.g. financial signatories) are found also in the EC portal.

We have a CHARTER E-duuni workspace available for WPS and other working groups. Arto Vitikka and Sirpa Rasmus can create and share folders and help with technical problems; they also update the CHARTER mail lists / list servers.

A NOTE ON SUSTAINABILITY

As we are promoting sustainable use of resources together with people living in the Arctic, we take the sustainability of the proposed project itself seriously. CHARTER will:

- maximize use of virtual meetings and minimize unnecessary travel
- related to that, conduct only necessary field work and utilize existing data, combine workshops and field work planned in different work packages as often as possible
- when travel is required use low carbon transport (night trains, most fuel-efficient cars etc.)
- make use of green facilities for all laboratory work and green equipment purchases
- maximize use of online peer-review journals for scientific dissemination
- limit office paper printing

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OPERATIONAL MANAGEMENT AND WORK PACKAGE LEADERS

The operational management of the project is made at WP level and is coordinated by the Project Office. WP leaders interface to the rest of the project through the PMG. **A Project Management Group (PMG)** handles required decision making on this level; the group consists of the project manager and all WP leaders (WPL). The group meets monthly. PMG reports on status of activities, milestones and deliverables per WP to Steering Committee every 6 months; these progress reports are coordinated by the Project Office.

All work packages and their leaders are responsible for managing their WPs as self-contained entities. The WPLs will have managerial responsibility for the collaboration of the other partners involved in the WP. The responsibilities of the WPLs include coordinating, monitoring, reporting and ensuring that the expected output of the WP will be delivered.

The responsibilities of WPLs:

- Monitoring the planning and progress of the defined tasks and deliverables
- Managing the resources available within the WP to ensure timely, cost effective and quality deliverables. Solving problems within the WP as they arise;
- Managing information flow within the WP. Intra WP meetings should be organised at least every quarter, with additional meetings arranged as required;
- Providing the interface between their WP and dissemination activities in WP7.

The first PMG meeting was held in September 2020 and will be organized monthly. Members of the group can request additional ones. Meetings are virtual; email meetings are also possible.

The chairperson will give notice of a meeting in writing latest 14 days before the meeting; agenda will be sent latest 7 days before the meeting. Members can add an item to the original agenda by written notification.

The PMG meeting can deliberate and make decisions when two-thirds of the members are present or represented (quorum). Each member has one vote. Members may appoint a substitute (vice leader) to attend. Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds of the votes cast.

The chairperson produces written minutes of each meeting; draft will be sent to members within 10 calendar days; and the minutes are considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no member has sent an objection in writing.

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Project Management Group (PMG) members are as follows:

- WP1 leader Annett Bartsch (co-lead: Timo Kumpula)
- WP2 leader Sari Stark (co-lead: Dorothee Ehrich)
- WP3 leader Otto Habeck (co-lead: Andrei Marin)
- WP4 leader Marc Macias Fauria (co-lead: Signe Normand)
- WP5 leader Heidrun Matthes (c-lead: Cecile Menard)
- WP6 leader Jussi Eronen
- WP7 leader Bruce Forbes
- Project management: Sirpa Rasmus / Leena Leppänen / Teresa Komu

WP-leaders can be contacted using their personal email addresses, or using a list server: CHARTER_WP-leaders@ulapland.fi

STEERING COMMITTEE

A Steering Committee (SC) forms the main decision-making body of the project. The Steering Committee's main responsibility is overall follow-up the progress of the project, especially with respect to Deliverables and Milestones and also to contribute to the technical, financial, legal, administrative, ethical, and dissemination issues of the project. Other responsibilities for the SC are to address any changes in the project execution that may affect Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement (in consultation with EC) and resolve possible conflicts.

The following issues require approval by the SC:

- The dissemination plan
- Reporting to EC - progress, management and financial reports
- Any changes to the Consortium Agreement or Grant Agreement e.g. budgetary changes
- Changes in the direction or content of the project (for discussion with EC representatives)
- Evolution of the Consortium
- Declaration of a partner as a defaulting party and definition of rectification actions
- Content, finances and intellectual property rights

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The CHARTER SC consists of one representatives of each partner. Nominated SC members are deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate and make decisions. The SC will be chaired by the PI (Forbes). The project manager will also attend as a rapporteur of the project. The agenda for the SC meeting will encompass the current status and progress of the CHARTER project compared to plan. The SC discusses and takes necessary decisions on the project's overall direction and priorities, as well as on the overall performance of tasks and activities. Risks will be identified as early as possible, and actions will be taken to mitigate the consequences. Problematic issues regarding content and finances will be discussed and appropriate decisions taken.

The SC shall collect information every 6 months on the progress of the project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the project with the plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the plan. The SC will support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the funder and in preparing related data and deliverables. The SC is free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions. In addition, proposals made by the WP leaders or EAG members will also be considered and decided upon by the SC.

First SC meeting will be arranged back to back with the CHARTER kick-off meeting in October 2021 and then annually. Members of the group can request additional meetings. Meetings can be in person or virtual, or even email meetings if necessary. Half-year meetings (on progress reports between the annual meetings) will be virtual or email meetings.

The chairperson will give notice of a meeting in writing latest 45 days before the meeting; agenda will be sent latest 21 days before the meeting. Members can add an item to the original agenda by written notification, latest 14 days before the meeting.

The SC meeting can deliberate and make decisions when two-thirds of the members are present or represented (quorum). Each member has one vote. Members may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend. Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds of the votes cast.

The chairperson produces written minutes of each meeting; draft will be sent to members within 10 calendar days; and the minutes are considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no member has sent an objection in writing.

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CHARTER Steering Committee members are as follows:

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1	LAY	University of Lapland	Finland	Bruce Forbes bruce.forbes@ulapland.fi
2	NTNU	Norw. Univ. of Science and Technology	Norway	James Speed james.speed@ntnu.no
3	UCL	University College London	UK	Julienne Stroeve j.stroeve@ucl.ac.uk
4	NMBU	Norwegian University of Life Sciences	Norway	Andrei Marin andrei.marin@nmbu.no
5	UOXF	University of Oxford	UK	Marc Macias-Fauria marc.maciasfauria@ouce.ox.ac.uk
6	UH	University of Helsinki	Finland	Jussi Eronen jussi.t.eronen@helsinki.fi
7	UEF	University of Eastern Finland	Finland	Timo Kumpula timo.kumpula@uef.fi
8	BGEOS	b.geos GmbH	Austria	Annett Bartsch annett.bartsch@bgeos.com
9	LBHI	Agricultural University of Iceland	Iceland	Isabel Barrio isabel@lbhi.is
10	FMI	Finnish Meteorological Institute	Finland	Jouni Pulliainen jouni.pulliainen@fmi.fi
11	UZH	University of Zurich	Switzerland	Gabriela Schaeppman-Strub gabriela.schaeppman@ieu.uzh.ch
12	UTU	University of Turku	Finland	Nora Fagerholm ncfage@utu.fi
13	WSL	Swiss Fed. Inst. for Forest, Snow and Landscape Res.	Switzerland	Christian Rixen rixen@slf.ch
14	UHAM	University of Hamburg	Germany	Otto Habeck otto.habeck@uni-hamburg.de
15	AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute	Germany	Heidrun Matthes heidrun.matthes@awi.de
16	UiT	The Arctic University of Norway	Norway	Dorothee Ehrich dorothee.ehrich@uit.no
17	UEDIN	University of Edinburgh	UK	Isla Myers-Smith isla.myers-smith@ed.ac.uk
18	NINA	The Norwegian Inst. for Nature Research	Norway	Cathrine Henaug catherine.henaug@nina.fi
19	ULIV	University of Liverpool	UK	Richard Bradshaw

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				Richard.Bradshaw@liverpool.ac.uk
20	AU	Aarhus University	Denmark	Signe Normand signe.normand@bios.au.dk
21	UmU	Umeå University	Sweden	Johan Olofsson johan.olofsson@emg.umu.se

EXPERT ADVISORY GROUP

The project will include inputs from the Expert Advisory Group (EAG). The EAG will consist of selected experts who have understanding of the project content and can discuss the interests of stakeholder groups and how the project can benefit the society and communicate with it. The experts represent, among others, ministries, reindeer herders and science communication professionals. The EAG will maintain close contact with the project and it can raise critical questions, comments and recommendations to the project partners. The EAG acts also as a bridge between the actual project and wider society, thus also enhancing the dialogue with policy makers. The EAG will be briefed by the project leader or project manager and, when relevant, other project personnel. In the beginning of the project, we will establish the EAG with original members. Additional and/or replacement members will be engaged as and when deemed necessary by the Steering Committee or the EAG.

First meeting of the EAG will be organized in November 2020 and then annually.
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The original members of the CHARTER Expert Advisory Group are as follows:

- Markku Heikkilä, Head of Science Communications Unit, Arctic Centre, University of Lapland, Finland (chair)
- Aulikki Alanen, Environment Counsellor / Biodiversity, Ministry of the Environment, Finland
- Inge Danielsen, Saami Reindeer Herders' Association, Norway
- Niklas Labba, Saarivuoma sameby, Sweden/Norway
- Annette Löf, Researcher at Vaartoe-Centre for Sami Research, Umeå University and Div. of Environmental Communication, Swedish Univ. of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
- Maria Atamas, Department for the Coordination of Scientific Activities and Vice-Director of the Administration of Inter-Regional and Scientific Activities, Yamal-Nenets Autonomous Okrug, Russia

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- Tapani Sirviö, Ministerial advisor, Future of Reindeer Husbandry in Finland Working Group; Nordic Ministerial Working Group on Reindeer Husbandry, Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Finland

The EAG can be contacted through the chair of the group, Markku Heikkilä:
markku.heikkila@ulapland.fi +358404844300